

Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for
smaller enterprises in Europe

D8.10- The SENTINEL project handbook - second version

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
API	Application Programming Interface
CERTs	Computer Emergency Response Teams
CSIRTs	Computer Security Incident Response Teams
DB	Database
DEM	Dissemination and Exploitation Manager
DoA	Description of Action
DoW	Description of Work
DPA	Data Protection Authority
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EDAC	Ethical & Data privacy Advisory Committee
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IdMS	Identity Management System
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
IPRC	Intellectual Property Right Committee
KR	Key Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LP	Lead Partner of Deliverable
PC	Project Coordinator
PCO	Project Coordination Office
PM	Person Months
QAM	Quality Assurance Manager
QR	Quarterly Report
SMEs/MEs	Small-Medium Enterprises / Micro-Enterprises
STIM	Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager
TL	Task Leader
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
WG	Working Group
WGL	Working Group Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This document represents the project management handbook which is created to address all the general internal management procedures that have been adopted during SENTINEL's project lifecycle. It has been developed in the framework of *WP8 – Project Management, Coordination and Quality Assurance* of the SENTINEL project under Grand Agreement n°101021659.

The purpose of the handbook is to facilitate the management of the project, monitoring the overall progress and communication between partners and the European Commission. The handbook includes the project management structure and procedures, partner contact information, deliverable review and submission procedures, dispute resolution procedures, and reporting procedures. Finally, it includes a preliminary list of risks for the implementation of the action and contingency plans in case they materialize.

This deliverable comes in three versions within the whole project lifetime. This is the second version which revises and updates the first version published in M4 and will be finalized at the last project year through the production of the third and complete version of this document.

The handbook should be used by all SENTINEL partners as a reference manual during the implementation of the action. It is intended to be a living document that will be updated whenever required to reflect up-to-date information.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This handbook was developed by the SENTINEL project to document the procedures to be adopted as far as the effective management and needs are concerned. The handbook contains the project management structure and procedures, partner contact information, deliverable review and submission procedures, procedures for dispute resolution and reporting procedures. This document initially provides an overview of the project topic and goals, then illustrates its objectives along with their relation to the work programme. Subsequently, it references the management procedures, which are described in detail in D8.5 “*The SENTINEL QA scheme & periodic monitoring report – first version*”, submitted in M3 (August 2021). Moreover, this version references the D8.8 “*The Project Handbook – first version*”, submitted in M4 (September 2021).

1.2 Intended Readership

This document is intended both for consortium members and external to the project stakeholders, since it comprises a rich information content platform about the project’s main principles, components, participants, latest news, and upcoming actions.

1.3 Project Executive Summary

More than 25 million European SMEs/MEs, following the EU business policy, are facing multiple challenges related to the protection of personal data. This results in a non-practical roadmap for compliance and in ranging from awareness. On the contrary to large enterprises, SMEs/MEs do not have the access into corporate-level cybersecurity technology and capacity-building for compliance, making them increasingly victims costly data breaches.

SENTINEL aims to bridge the security and personal data protection gap for European SMEs/MEs by raising awareness and boosting their cyber capabilities through innovation at a cost-effective level. This vision is realized by integrating tried-and-tested security and privacy technologies into a unified digital architecture and then applying disruptive Intelligence for compliance.

Overall, SENTINEL provides a complete privacy, cybersecurity and data protection suite, combined with a well-researched methodology for application, knowledge sharing hub and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation. Thus, it enables small and medium enterprises to achieve business security, safeguard their and customers’ assets in an efficient and affordable manner.

1.4 Objectives

Briefly, the objectives of SENTINEL project are listed below:

Objective 1: Develop and support an end-to-end digital Privacy and Personal Data Protection (PDP) compliance framework and Identity Management System (IdMS) that enables Speed, Flexibility, Quality, Efficiency and Security for SMEs/MEs.

Objective 2: Provide technological advances in SMEs/MEs' data protection compliance assessment, such as technologies on automated compliance, cybersecurity and protection, tailor-

made automated requirements engineering as a service, machine (deep) learning and anomaly detection, a unified Identity Management System, and ML-facilitated multi-criteria recommendation systems.

Objective 3: Provide novel tools and services for enabling highly automated PD P compliance in SMEs/MEs, leveraging innovative collection of self-serving, state-of-the-art security and privacy enhancing modules, both open-source and contributed by consortium partners.

Objective 4: Consolidate international and European links, raise awareness, collaborate with standardisations bodies, and ensure the technology transfer of project's results via EU digital innovation hubs.

Objective 5: Boost the effectiveness of the EU data economy, by offering high TRL solutions (TRL 6-7).

Objective 6: Validate, demonstrate, and carry out experimental evaluation of the proposed framework on real-world SMEs/MEs operation scenarios.

1.5 Relation to the Work Programme

SENTINEL's relation to the work programme (SU-DS03-2019-2020 "*Digital Security and privacy for citizens and Small and Medium Enterprises and Micro Enterprises*") is described as follows:

- SENTINEL will a) deliver an innovative privacy and personal data protection compliance digital architecture which addresses the precise challenge for privacy through robust, enterprise-grade cybersecurity; b) give SMEs/MEs a more central role in offering data protection and complying with regulations, also empowering citizens to own their personal data and feel more secure through enabling an EU-wide personal data space.
- SENTINEL clearly addresses to SMEs and will offer assessment and self-configuration of security and privacy policies. The project will place total control for privacy and security within their reach by a) digitally transforming existing methodologies and tools to comprehensive self-assessment capabilities, b) offering intelligent security recommendations, policy drafting and privacy assurance for compliance and c) allowing customers (and effectively all EU citizens) to own and assert control over their personal data.
- Consent management, with configurable granularity, is a key component in delivering SENTINEL's personal data protection compliance framework, along with several key features such as permission management, data model management, personal data storage and value transfer mechanisms which effectively deliver SENTINEL's Identity Management system that allows true data portability- the way EU envisions it. However, technology alone cannot 'do the trick'. Widespread citizen awareness, coupled with governance support is just as crucial for bringing both ends together. SENTINEL invests in a structured dissemination strategy which centres around public consultation sessions, towards establishing an open dialogue with the society and key stakeholders.
- The SENTINEL IdMS will deliver key integrations in the form of plug-in modules for many commercial and open-source applications (such as Cloud ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning), eCommerce, web apps, sales automation / CRM, marketing automation etc.) used by SMEs/MEs. These apps' secure end-to-end secure access to personal data, owned solely

by the individuals, will be thoroughly logged for accountability, and audited by end users. This includes the capability of revoking or fine-tuning access granularity.

- SENTINEL partners acknowledge challenges that most SMEs/MEs face, and have placed them centrally in the project planning, leading to an innovative value proposition stating that SMEs/MEs can and will benefit from enterprise-grade, intelligent, and decentralised privacy and personal data protection management services provision without expensive dedicated human resources or know-how and at a lower overall low total cost.
- Knowledge interchange and learning has been another pivotal concern in SENTINEL, for which the consortium partners have planned a dedicated component group in the project's conceptual architecture. It is named the Observatory and it provides a flexible security knowledge hub, providing (a) a centralised Knowledge Base (KB), aggregating information about recently identified data and privacy breaches, and related evidence, coupled with collaboration tools; (b) an open API platform to exchange this information with open security data hubs, such as open source incident response platforms, Computer Emergency Response Teams (CERTs) and Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) and (c) an intelligent module to coordinate policy reuse elements when automatically drafting new security and privacy policies for participants.

Relation with the specific sub-topic (b) "Small and Medium-sized Enterprises and Micro Enterprises (SMEs&MEs): defenders of security, privacy, and personal data protection"

- The scope of SENTINEL is precisely democratising access to a plethora of cybersecurity and privacy and personal data protection components, some of which, such as CyberRange simulations, forensic analyses, advanced web app security and intrusion detection systems (IDS) have traditionally only been considered in the security domain for larger enterprises. These contributed security and privacy solutions complemented by open-source offerings to be ultimately selected for the precise needs and budget of each participant SME/ME by the intelligent recommendation engine, making sure their needs are addressed as efficiently and narrowly targeted as possible.
- Self-assessment and monitoring within SENTINEL's Holistic GDPR, Privacy and Personal Data Protection compliance framework will be achieved by the Self-assessment centre, which provides continuous feedback and real-time monitoring for SME via the MySentinel Dashboard. Forecasting is achieved through intelligent recommendations and informed policy drafting.
- SENTINEL will establish a strong feedback loop between all information-bearing sources of interest to the specific domain and characteristics of participant SMEs/MEs. This channel is set between i) the Observatory/knowledge hub which exchanges data with a) open/public sources and b) the Digital Core's Incident handling and sharing module and ii) the MySentinel Dashboard which presents contextually rich information with emphasis on completeness and user experience. Critical information on latest threats, zero-day attacks, dangerous malware etc. are also disseminated with urgency over multiple channels such as email, mobile notifications and public aggregators.

- SENTINEL effectively proposes a novel “one-stop shop” approach to integrated and obtainable privacy and personal data protection compliance model for smaller enterprises. The ease of use and affordability of the integrated solution is guaranteed by (a) the centralised, all-encompassing conceptual architecture, (b) an intelligent recommendation engine making automated but informed decisions primarily based on participant’s budgetary and resource allocation constraints.
- Building on-line collaboration between SMEs/MEs associations and with CERTs/CSIRTs is precisely another key objective of the SENTINEL Observatory, empowering both human and machine (API-enabled) collaboration on the exchange of critical data and knowledge over threats, signatures, evidence, incident data etc. between SME/ME associations, CERTs, CSIRTs and DPAs, not just for incident reporting but also for more efficient handling and mitigation.
- CyberRange play a very central role in SENTINEL, in the sense of bringing an enterprise-grade security simulation and training technology to smaller businesses. Collaborating with industry-leading player Airbus, SENTINEL will offer SMEs/MEs access to CyberRange as a practical and efficient approach for conducting hands-on cybersecurity simulations, training, and cybersecurity technology development without costly and tedious external security consulting processes.
- SENTINEL will ensure the effective integration of all its functionality into a fully working approach consisting of digital tools, a methodology and archetypal solutions to TRL 7.

2. Management Structure and Procedures

The project management structure and procedures have been presented in detail in Deliverable D8.5 (submitted in M3 of the project). The project management structure aims at guaranteeing the proper progress and to control the project with respect to the project objectives and plans ensuring both the technical coordination amongst the partners and the strict enforcing of the max expenses budget. It was defined to clearly identify the responsible members of the various partners of the Consortium, as well as to optimise the communication between the various partners and coordinating committees.

In addition, the management structure has been defined to secure reaching the project objectives within the given schedule while trying to reduce the management effort in the project to its minimum considering the number of partners. Although all partners in the project will actively participate in the management activities and are represented at the appropriate level, the project coordinator has tried to allocate a minimum manpower effort to them.

The project's Consortium Agreement (CA) includes among others, preventive measures for arrangement of IPR, exploitation rights, confidentiality, decision-making and change-procedures, cooperation, and exploitation after the project.

The structure of the project management is shown in Figure 1, and described in detail hereafter. It reviews conceptually the major parts of the project management structure, how the individual building blocks are interlinked and how management functions work.

Figure 1. SENTINEL's overview of the Project Management Structure

The project management structure is mainly composed of the following seven (7) entities:

- The **Project Coordinator (PC)**, who is responsible for the coordination activities under the Grant Agreement signed with the EC.
- The **General Assembly (GA)**, which is responsible for the general/administrative management of the project and comprises the highest decision body.
- The **External Advisory Board (EAB)**, which comprises a panel of four (4) independent experts that evaluates the project progress with respect to the main objectives and technological developments, as well as the dissemination and exploitation efforts.
- The Scientific, Technical & Innovation Manager (STIM), who is responsible for the overall technical project management and coordination of the work packages.
- The Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM), who is responsible for the dissemination and exploitation activities during the project lifecycle.
- The Quality Assurance Manager (QAM), who is responsible for overseeing the quality of the project tasks and deliverables.
- The **Ethics & Data Privacy Advisory Committee (EDAC)**, which is responsible for ensuring that all actions throughout the project implementation (e.g., deliverables, innovation activities, research methodology, research impact, pilot execution) abide with European and, national, legal, and ethical requirements and that personal rights are always respected.
- **Work Package Leader (WPLs)**, who coordinate WP work and are monitored by the project's STIM (Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager).
- **Task Leaders (TLs)**, who coordinate task work and are monitoring by the corresponding WPL.
- **Working Group Leaders (WGLs)**, who are responsible for developing and curating the corresponding Contexts of the revised architecture (see D1.2, submitted in M6).

2.1 Roles

2.1.1 Project Coordinator

The **Project Coordinator (PC)** is responsible for both the general and administrative management, and the scientific and technical management of the entire project. The PC monitors the planning, progress, and deliverables issues of the project with respect to the objectives and plans described in the project's Description of Work (DoW). If necessary, PC initiates corrective actions for the deviations. The PC is responsible for the knowledge management within the project, the management of innovation related activities and IPR, the dissemination and exploitation activities. The PC is also the unique interface between the project and the European Commission. The PC manages all the communications to/from the EU Commission, the periodic reporting and he will organize the review meetings with the Project Officer.

The PC is also responsible for collecting financial statements and audit certificates, as required by the contract. The PC is responsible for reporting the periodic financial summaries and resource efforts spent by each partner. The PC manages the granted EU contribution and the distribution of the funds to each partner according with the actual allocated efforts. The PC convenes the GA. Regarding the scientific/technical management activities, the PC leads the GA and assists, when necessary, the Work Package Leaders and makes sure that the communication between the various work packages proceeds as smoothly as possible for a successful integration of the various components of the project.

- Dr. George Bravos is the PC for the project.

Table 1. Project Coordinator information

Name	Dr. George Bravos
Address	Information Technology for Market Leadership (ITML) 22 Katechaki Str., Athens, Greece
Postal Code	GR 11525
Telephone	+30 211 800 1862
Fax	-
Email	gebravos@itml.gr

2.1.2 Project Coordination Office

The **Project Coordination Office (PCO)** (as part of the coordinator's staff) assists the PC in the administrative management and is located at the coordinator's site. The PCO is staffed by the Project Coordinator, a secretary, and a technical support person. The main responsibilities include:

- Ensure efficient communication among the partners using tools such as mailing lists, wiki, websites, plenary project meetings, etc.
- Prepare the project meetings, including scheduling, agenda preparation, minute taking, etc.
- Collect documentation for monitoring the activities within the work packages and for the preparation of the Annual Reports.
- Collect deliverables for submission to the Commission.
- Prepare and submit the Consortium Agreement (CA).
- Promote gender equality.
- Handle the financial tasks, such as cost statements, payment distribution, obtaining audit certificates from each participant, etc.
- Prepare and update the project calendar, establish mailing lists, set up a secure internet platform for the exchange of project data and information; and
- Support the management of knowledge.

2.1.3 General Assembly

The **General Assembly (GA)** is a body consisting of one representative from each partner in the Consortium, with the task to supervise the project and will be chaired by the PC. The GA meets at least every six months (physically or virtually) or, if necessary, more often for project progress. Meetings can also be held as phone-conferences. The GA provides a forum for the discussion of administrative and strategic management of the project and for the monitoring of dissemination and exploitation activities. In addition, the GA decides on approving major modifications to project

plans, allocated efforts, budget issues and possible addition of new partners. The GA provides a forum for the discussion of major changes in the project work plan and directions in response to new problems or new situations. In voting at the GA, each partner shall have one vote and decisions will be taken by consensus. Modifications to the work plans in the DoA will require the consensus or a 2/3 majority (i.e., 8 out of 13 partners).

The below table represents the updated GA members of the SENTINEL project, as some changes have been occurred within the previous months.

Table 2. SENTINEL’s General Assembly members

No.	Partner	Member	Alternate
1	ITML	George Bravos	Siranush Akarmazyan
2	LIST	Philippe Valoggia	Djamel Khadraoui
3	SHELL	<i>The partner SHELL has been terminated from ECAS</i>	
4	IDIR	Peri Loucopoulos	Yannis Skourtis
5	INTRA	Spyros Evangelatos	Manolis Falelakis
6	STS	George Spanoudakis	Andreas Miaoudakis
7	AEGIS	Ilias Spais	Marinos Tsantekidis
8	TSI	Sotiris Ioannidis	Giorgos Tsirantonakis
9	ACS	Thomas Oudin	Paul-Emmanuel Brun
10	UNINOVA	Ruben Costa	Cláudio Corrêa Filho
11	CG	Christopher Konialis	Mihalis Roukounakis
12	TIG	Yannis Loucopoulos	Daryl Holkham
13	CECL	Dimitra Malandraki	Zoe Kasapi
14	FP	Elma Kalogeraki	Spyridon Papastergiou

2.1.4 Work Package Leader and Task Leaders

The **Work Package Leader (WPL)** is appointed by the partner responsible for the respective work package. Their role is to coordinate the day-to-day work carried out in the work package (WP) and ensure the communication and collaboration of the WP contributors. The WPLs are responsible for the planning and monitoring of the WP activities, as well as for ensuring the scheduled write-up of the WP deliverables via close collaboration with the Task Leaders (see below). The WPL should organize WP Meetings for scientific/technical discussions for that specific WP. The WP Meetings (physical or as phone conferences) are organized monthly or more frequently if special issues need to be handled. The WPL should coordinate the interaction and collaboration with other WPs and to facilitate the communication in and between WPs. The WPL reports the progress and criticisms (if any) to the GA.

In more detail, the WPL responsibilities are:

- Coordinate, monitor and manage the activities under their responsibility.
- Ensure the timely achievement of the objectives and milestones of the work packages.
- Prepare the internal and external reports (deliverables) expected for the work package and assist in the production of the overall management reports of the project.
- Regularly meet or hold conference calls with the PC and arrange regular technical meetings or conference calls with the work package members.

- Ensure the accurate recording of times, costs, and resources, and report any discrepancies immediately to the PC.
- Organize technical presentations of the work package activities, and to ensure proper involvement and visibility of the active member.
- Inform the GA about progress of activities and possible critical issues.
- Identify the need for creation of separate tasks in the work package horizontal information flow to other work package leaders.
- Identify and report any technical or managerial problems that arise in their work package.

Table 3. Work Package Leaders

No.	Name	Leader	Organisation
WP1	SENTINEL baseline: Setting the Methodological Scene	Peri Loucopoulos	IDIR
WP2	The SENTINEL privacy and personal data protection technologies	Philippe Valoggia	LIST
WP3	The SENTINEL digital core	Christos Dimou	ITML
WP4	The SENTINEL services	Thomas Oudin	ACS
WP5	SENTINEL continuous integration and system validation	Spyros Evangelatos	INTRA
WP6	SENTINEL continuous integration and system validation	Christopher Konialis	CG
WP7	Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management	Ruben Costa	UNINOVA
WP8	Project Management, Coordination and Quality Assurance	Siranush Akarmazyan	ITML
WP9	Ethics requirements	Siranush Akarmazyan	ITML

Task Leaders (TLs) are appointed by the partner responsible for each work package task. The TLs of tasks belonging to the same work package are coordinated by the respective WPL. Their objective is to coordinate the day-to-day work carried out in each task and to ensure communication among the task participants. The TLs are also responsible for the planning and monitoring of the task activities and for ensuring the scheduled issue of the task outcomes (deliverables). For each task, multiple people from contributing partners may be responsible for driving the work. However, typically, the bulk of the work is carried out by the organization of the TL.

2.1.5 Scientific-Technical-Innovation Manager

The **Scientific - Technical – Innovation Manager (STIM)** is appointed by the PC and is responsible for the overall technical project management and coordination of the work packages. The STIM is also the first deputy of the PC for all non-administrative issues and project representation.

- Dr. Manolis Falelakis (INTRA, manolis.falelakis@netcompany-intrasoft.com) has been assigned as STIM for the project.

2.1.6 Quality Assurance Manager

The **Quality Assurance Manager (QAM)** is appointed by the PC and is responsible for the coordination of the SENTINEL evaluation process, by coordinating and giving guiding support to the evaluation activity of each of the participating partners. In SENTINEL, the evaluation work is planned, coordinated, and monitored from the start of the project. A mechanism for reviewing progress against the success criteria identified by the GA has been already defined in the Quality Assurance Plan of D8.5 (submitted in M3). The QAM will ensure that goals set by the GA are fully implemented on a day-to-day basis.

- Dr. Tatiana Trantidou (ITML, t.trantidou@itml.gr) and Dr. Siranush Akarmazyan (ITML, siranush@itml.gr) have been assigned for the role of QAM for the project.

2.1.7 Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM)

The **Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM)** is responsible for the Dissemination and Exploitation activities of SENTINEL as described in WP7. DEM coordinates the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities during the project lifecycle. The policies for the dissemination of knowledge from the project, e.g., newsletters and joint publications, along with the exploitation of foreground and background knowledge have been set out in the Consortium Agreement. However, especially for the exploitation, each individual partner may decide the way its foreground and background are exploited.

- Mr. Ruben Costa (UNINOVA, rddc@uninova.pt) has been assigned as DEM for the project.

2.1.8 Ethical & Data privacy Advisory Committee (EDAC)

The **Ethics Advisory and Data privacy Committee (EDAC)** undertakes the following activities (i) ensures that personal rights are respected, (ii) understands potential uses of user information within SENTINEL, (iii) ensures that deliverables and innovation activities meet national legal and ethical requirements, (iv) addresses any rising research methodology ethical issues, (v) addresses any rising research impact ethical issues, (vi) identifies guidance with which SENTINEL should comply. The EDAC has been formed during M3 as per SENTINEL's GA and consists of 3 members:

- Prof. Fereniki Panagopoulou (CECL)
- Dr. Christopher Konialis (CG)
- Dr. Tal Soffer (external – Tel Aviv University)

2.1.9 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The **External Advisory Board (EAB)** includes a panel of four (4) relevant external stakeholders from any industry related to the management of sensitive data, the public and private sectors not involved in the day-to-day project work. This panel provides an outside view on SENTINEL and evaluates the overall progress with respect to the high-level objectives. We expect these experts to contribute significant ideas regarding the challenges and opportunities of the emerging research field of end-to-end security from an industrial perspective and thus ensure maximum impact of the SENTINEL project. All EAB members are invited to provide comments and modifications regarding requirements, objectives, and development, as well as exploitation and

dissemination activities. The EAB does not make any decisions but issue recommendations that will be discussed and processed at the following GA meeting. The EAB can also recommend calling additional EAB meetings that focus on specific topics or inviting additional experts to join the EAB. The experts comprising the EAB are presented below:

Table 4. External Advisory Board members

Member	Position	Company
Prof. João Mendonça	Assistant Professor	University of Minho, Campus de Gualtar, Portugal
Mr Toomas Lepik	Senior Information Security expert, SME owner	IT Kool Ja Konsultatsioonid OÜ, Brussels, Belgium
Mr Rodrigo Diaz	Head of Cybersecurity Unit	ATOS Research & Innovation department, Barcelona, Spain
Mr Stephanos Camarinopoulos	Director	RISA Sicherheitsanalysen GmbH, Berlin, Germany

2.1.10 Working Groups Leaders (WGLs)

The consortium has introduced a more relevant and efficient way to cluster and organize the technical work, directly mapping onto the revised architecture (see D1.2, submitted in M6). Four (4) Working Groups have been defined: (i) MySentinel; (ii) Self-Assessment; (iii) Core; and (iv) Observatory. As per their names, WGs are responsible for developing and curating the corresponding “contexts” of the revised architecture. Each WG has a go-to organization that orchestrates the work and acts as a contact point. WGs are monitored and report to the STIM.

Table 5. Working Groups Leaders

WG	WGL	Contact person	Correlation with WPs and tasks	Involved contexts/modules
MySentinel	AEGIS	Marinos Tsantekidis	WP5 (T5.1)	MySENTINEL dashboard, including all User Interfaces
Self-Assessment	STS	Kostas Poulivos	WP2 (T2.1), WP4 (T4.2, T4.3)	Self-assessment engine, SA tools, SME Profiles DB
Core	ITML	Christos Dimou	WP2 (T2.3, T2.4), WP3 (T3.2, T3.3, T3.4)	Recommendation Engine, Policy drafting, Policy Enforcement, Plugins repo, Trainings repo, Notification Aggregator, Incident Reporting
Observatory	ITML	Christos Dimou	WP3 (T3.1, T3.2, T3.4), WP4 (T4.4)	Data reuse policy, Policies repo, Incident Broker, Observatory KB, Observatory Information Exchange

2.2 Decision-making Mechanisms

The **Work Package Leader (WPL)** takes technical decisions at WP level. If technical decisions with consequences for the work in other WPs are taken, the WPL takes these decisions after consulting the PC and all other WPLs. The GA will take technical decisions at project level.

Decisions of the GA are binding for the project. Table 6 summarizes the decision-making responsibilities, while Table 7 presents the decision-making process.

Table 6. Decision making responsibilities

Activity	Decision by	Main input
Change workplan, shift project activities between partners, assign tasks of defaulting partners to others.	GA	PC+WPL
Approval of activity reports and deliverables to the EC.	QAM	PC+WPL
Inclusion or withdrawal of partners	GA	PC+WPL
Appointment of GA members.	GA	PC+WPL
Appointment of new WPL.	GA	PC+WPL

Table 7. Decision making process

Level	Decision Mechanism	Escalate if
WP	Verbal consensus	No consensus reached, Appeal to GA
GA	Verbal consensus, vote, if necessary, simple majority	No consensus reached, Appeal to PC
GA	Verbal mandatory, two-third majority needed, minutes taken	Intervention by the European Commission, or legal action, is the only escalation possible

2.3 Plenary Meetings

It has been demonstrated from past experience of the Consortium members that the needed interventions during the lifecycle of the project can be accurate, fast, and efficient. A fluent internal communication in the Consortium is foreseen to timely identify unexpected problems and purpose its effective handling, as described above. The Project Technical Committee will meet between 4 to 6 times per year (physical or virtual), or whenever required during the implementation of Consortium activities as described in the Consortium work plan. Additional meetings may be organized if needed. The meetings will normally be scheduled to rotate between the partners' home base or in any other way that is convenient for the partners.

The PC has organized the kick-off meeting with all partners in M1 (June 2021). The purpose of the project kick-off meeting was to check the effective beginning of the work detecting and preventing in the very beginning phase possible problems like, for example, delays in the personnel hiring procedures or device ordering.

The first plenary meeting took place in M4 (15-16 September 2021), hosted by UNINOVA in Guimaraes, Portugal, and was a hybrid meeting, enabling both physical and remote attendance by the SENTINEL partners. The purpose of this meeting was (i) to review progress of active work packages (i.e., WP1, WP7 and WP8), (ii) provide a coherent roadmap and plan work ahead until M10 for all work packages, (iii) review deliverables and KPIs status, (iv) organize a technical workshop with (external to the project) SMEs and MEs to present SENTINEL offerings and engage potential stakeholders for future testing within the context of pilot 3.

The second plenary meeting took place in M8 (20-21 January 2022), hosted by ITML in Athens, Greece, and despite the constraints imposed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the hybrid nature of the meeting brought together most of the consortium members by giving them the opportunity to make constructive discussions about both technical and non-technical subjects. The partners had also the chance to join the plenary remotely. The main purpose of the meeting was to present the results achieved so far and produce a solid plan towards the 1st version of the SENTINEL technologies and services. The project Work Packages (WPs), the SENTINEL core services, the MVP release, were the main topics that triggered a fruitful conversation among the partners during the first day of the meeting. A major part of the 2nd day focused on presentations and discussions on the status of Key Results (KR) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), the SENTINEL pilot activities as well as the project's communication and dissemination approaches. The second plenary meeting also hosted a special session dedicated to EAB members, where 3 out of 4 members of the EAB committed joined (2 physically and one remotely) in a discussion with the rest of the consortium, provided constructive criticism and their thoughts for future improvements and directions.

The third plenary meeting took place in M12 (5-6th May 2022), hosted by TSI in Chania, Greece, and was a hybrid meeting, enabling both physical and remote attendance by the SENTINEL partners. The main focus of the meeting was to review progress in all WPs since M8, hold an extensive technical workshop whose purpose was to (i) present the current version of the MVP release and (ii) technical developments that will be presented as part of M12 deliverables. The plenary also included a preparation session for the upcoming review meeting in M13. In addition, the meeting also hosted the 2nd SME-centric workshop, where more than 25 SMEs/MEs joined remotely to attend the workshop, ask questions on SENTINEL offerings and general GDPR issues, as well as answer a questionnaire that will enable the SENTINEL consortium to extract meaningful information about the participants and engage them as future end users.

2.4 Intellectual Property Rights and Publications Management

IPR management procedures, along with the management of joint publications, have been defined in the Consortium Agreement. The GA of SENTINEL will ensure that the commercial results are distributed in a fair and equitable manner that recognises the contributions of the inventors and the institution as well as those of other stakeholders and that both IP and other products of research are made available to the public through an efficient and timely process of technology transfer. Finally, it will establish standards for determining the rights and obligations of the SENTINEL partners, the creators of intellectual property and their sponsors, with respect to inventions, discoveries and work created.

If necessary, the GA may establish an Intellectual Property Rights Committee (IPRC) to deal with intellectual property that either is introduced to the project by a partner or produced as a work package outcome. The IPRC will be responsible for the definition of access rights and licensing (if required so) of the project results.

The SENTINEL partners have already established various Open Access policies: supporting authors in retaining their rights to provide access to published articles, providing official repositories, and making the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication available to OpenAIRE.

A 'Summary Guidelines on Open Accessibility' is already published in SENTINEL NextCloud repository and should be used for all the Scientific Papers. It can be found as SENTINEL_Open Access Guidelines_2022.docx.

SENTINEL will engage multiple stakeholders and develop an open-source information ecosystem with tools and knowledge available to all. Some of the project partners will be either using open-source code in their deliverables or contributing their deliverables to the open-source communities.

2.5 Conflict Resolution, Consensus Building and Corrective Actions

The problem handling and corrective action philosophy of the consortium in the first place is based on prevention. In case a problem arises, it will be tackled as soon as possible and at the lowest possible level, meanwhile bringing it to the immediate attention of the PC. Each partner of the consortium is responsible (liable) for the performance of any part of its share of the project or other EU contract obligation. In case, however, a partner miss- or under performs, this will be promptly documented.

Based on the project partners' extensive experience with previous H2020 projects under DS/ICT (DS-Digital Security/Information and Communication Technologies) topics, it has decided to adopt a conflict resolution template that has served very well in the past. The procedure works as follows:

The PC will try to solve the problem immediately by all possible means and, if necessary, an official letter will be sent by the PC to this partner (with notification to GA and maybe the EU Project Officer). Important decisions on different issues, technical or otherwise, pertaining to the project will be reached by consensus decision-making in the General Assembly. Meanwhile, if necessary, an extra GA meeting will be organised in order to solve such a problem and limit the impact for the project. When serious disputes arise, red-flag procedures can be initiated by any member of the consortium after alerting the PC about the issue that needs resolution.

All serious conflicts between consortium members will be handled and resolved by the General Assembly, allowing a maximum of 21 days from the identification of a conflict to the attempted final resolution. The PC is responsible for arranging a General Assembly meeting at its premises within this period. At least 75% of the partner representatives should be present at this meeting. Otherwise, the PC will intervene to settle the case. In the first instance, negotiation will seek to resolve the dispute(s). Should consensus not result, a majority vote will be used. Each General Assembly member has one vote and the PC, if necessary, will cast the tie-breaking vote. In the case of persistent or exceptional disputes which threaten the continuation of the project, the consortium will inform the project officer, solicit external advice, and call for a full meeting of the consortium members.

2.6 Effectiveness of the Proposed Management Structure

The proposed management structure will lead to an effective and efficient implementation of the SENTINEL project for several reasons:

- Its small size will allow decisions to be reached quickly and implemented as soon as they are reached.

- By including all core partners in the main decision-making body (i.e., the General Assembly) we give all the partners the right of participation, a feeling that they do not only contribute to the technical work, but that they also have a direct and immediate saying in the governance of the network, a feeling that they themselves are responsible for the successful implementation of the project. This usually works as an invaluable incentive for people to work harder towards achieving the goals of the project.
- Using the proposed management structure, (most of) the partners have collaborated effectively in past and ongoing projects, such as CYRENE, COLLABS, THREAT-ARREST, I-BiDaaS, and others. It is expected that this management structure will enable to achieve another success in the implementation of SENTINEL.
- The operation of the Quality Assurance Manager and the Technical Program Committee will safeguard and ensure the high quality of the project's results.

3. Document Management

NextCloud was selected as the software for the repository of the SENTINEL documents. The PC will be responsible for maintaining the following on the server:

- Quarterly reports
- Cost Claims
- Meeting agendas
- Meeting presentations
- Meeting Minutes/Action Items
- Teleconference Meeting Minutes
- Annual Project Reports
- Contractual Documentation
- Deliverables
- Technical Reports
- Technical Papers
- Dissemination, communication, and exploitation documentations
- Market Studies
- SENTINEL KPI Evaluation Matrix: *This has recently created by the PC*

3.1 Language

The official document and emails language is English. In case of official deliverables, effort shall be made to have a native English speaker review the deliverables when possible.

3.2 Web Server

The web server is set-up and hosted by ITML. The domain name registered for the project is ***sentinel-project.eu***.

The web server consists of a public part which is accessible by all visitors. The consortium will also consider a password protected part, if necessary, which will be accessible only by the SENTINEL partners. The public deliverables list will appear at the public part. The confidential deliverables will be password protected or be kept in the NextCloud.

3.3 Document Templates

The PC has created templates for different uses within the project (for more detail, see Deliverable D8.5), which are all available in NextCloud (folder *05_Templates*). For documents such as deliverables, Microsoft Word templates have been provided. It can be found in the project NextCloud repository as SENTINEL_Deliverables_template.docx.

Furthermore, for project-related presentations in external events as well as internal meetings, a PowerPoint template was created. It can be found in file SENTINEL_Presentation_Template.pptx in the NextCloud repository. For the corresponding minutes-of-meeting, the QAM has created the SENTINEL_Minutes_of_Meeting_template.pptx.

For the deliverables peer review process, the QAM has created an internal review plan, where partners have been assigned to peer review SENTINEL deliverables (two (2) reviewers per

deliverable) (see Deliverable D8.5). A peer review template has been created for this purpose and can be found in the shared repository as SENTINEL_Peer_review_document.docx.

Finally, the PC has provided a template reporting form, which will be used by the consortium partners to report on their progress on a quarterly basis. These quarterly reports will be annually compiled by the PC into the project progress report. The reporting form template is in Word format and can be found in file SENTINEL_tec_reporting_template.docx.

3.4 Document Exchange Methods

Documents will be exchanged primarily via upload to the NextCloud repository. After a successful document upload, the partner should also send an email with the document title and link. In case document uploading is not feasible or desirable (e.g., short-lived documents), email exchange will take place instead.

3.5 Document Naming

Proper document naming is required to keep track of the project technical and administrative resources. The official deliverable will be named using the naming format *SENTINEL_Dx.y_Deliverabletitle.ext*, where *x* and *y* are the numbers designating the deliverable as per the DoA, and *ext* is the extension (.docx, .pdf, .ppt, .xls, .zip, .exe). The underscore (_) between words is necessary to activate linking of the filename.

3.6 Documents Software Tools

For documents processing, the following tools are recommended:

- Document Processing: Microsoft Word (2010 or newer, for Mac or PC)
- Spreadsheet Processing: Microsoft Excel (2010 or newer, for Mac or PC)
- Presentation Processing: Microsoft PowerPoint (2010 or newer, for Mac or PC)
- Portable Document Format: Adobe Acrobat (2010 or newer, for Mac or PC)

In case a partner aims to use a different software tool, they have to ensure that the outcome is compatible with the above tools.

4. Communication

Ensuring good communication among the project partners and towards outside entities represents a key of success for the project and a fundamental practice to manage the project properly. The establishment of a fast, reliable, and easily accessible communications infrastructure is vital to the proper operation of a European project. This can only be achieved through the proper use of electronic communications (e.g., email, web-based exchanges). The project's website will also be used to enable fast and efficient exchanges of information.

The main communication channels of SENTINEL are:

- Email
- Web-based services/chats
- NextCloud
- Bilateral telephone/VoIP calls
- Telephone conferences
- Voice teleconferences supported by desktop sharing tools (e.g., Adobe)
- Physical meetings

The internal communication includes physical quarterly meetings, starting with the two-day kick-off meeting to guarantee in depth knowledge exchange (see Sections 2.3 & 6.1). Meetings are accompanied by monthly teleconferences to discuss project progress and to take decisions.

Also, SENTINEL heavily relies on the exchange of emails and the use of the NextCloud repository for document collaboration and other tasks. In addition, SENTINEL uses *GitHub* for software development, version control and source code management. The advantages of these tools lie in their functions of allowing sharing of documents and code (also tracking different versions), contact details, white boards, discussion rooms etc.

External communication includes the dissemination of all project results through publications, the project website, conferences, events, the EAB and the establishment of links with relevant projects and SME associations. It is well known that systematic and timely implementation of information flow is central for any consortium-based project. Nevertheless, information overload should obviously be avoided. The communication flow between the SENTINEL members will be implemented by:

- Periodic meetings of the GA
- Periodic meetings of the STIM together with all consortium members
- Periodic meetings of the DEM together with all consortium members
- Individual working meetings of members of each WP
- Individual working meetings of members of each WG together with the STIM
- Phone and e-mail interchanges (day to day cooperative working infrastructure)

The PC is and will be in a day-by-day communication and have the duty to communicate on a systematic and frequent basis. All ordinary messages related to a certain work package will be communicated among all partners involved in that work package. Any special issues or problems rising within a WP are going to be forwarded to the WP leader and to the GA members. Obviously, this formal and detailed *hierarchical communication flow*, does not exclude by any means *ad hoc*

direct communication between any partner participants, whenever this is important for the project success. The experience in running research projects and having previously worked together successfully and with good relationships almost ensures the avoidance of problems regarding communication and information flow along the development of the SENTINEL project.

4.1 Email Communication

ITML has set-up and maintains the following email lists:

- sentinel-members@lists.sentinel-project.eu for all members working on the project. This list is used for discussing all matters of the project.
- edac@lists.sentinel-project.eu for the members of the EDAC. This list is used to facilitate communication among the EDAC members only.

We have tried to keep a flat mailing list structure on purpose. We opted to have one general mailing list for everyone to keep everyone involved and updated on the work taking place in SENTINEL.

In case a new participant needs to be added to a list, send an email to: aanaxagorou@itml.gr

5. Resource Management, Reporting and Deliverables

For a more effective monitoring of the project, the PCO has introduced quarterly reports (QR) which are filled in by all consortium partners every three months (the template of the QR reports is provided in the appendix). These reports are internal, and they intend to facilitate monitoring of the progress of each individual WP, task and partners with regard to deliverables, milestones and KR/KPIs achieved. A resource planning in relation to the achieved progress up until M12 is also registered by the PC. In this respect, it summarizes of an overview of the resources spent by the consortium and will be reported in the Technical Review Meeting to be held in M13 (June 2022). Signed full cost statements will be delivered to the coordinator at M18, M30 and M36.

5.1 Quarterly Reports

The quarterly reports should be sent to the PC five (5) working days after the end of the reporting period. An appropriate template has already been created by the PC for this (see Section 3.3). The quarterly reports will include at least the following issues:

- Major achievements per partner
- Progress per work package
- Status of deliverables
- Deviations from the workplan
- Project Meetings/Teleconferences attended
- Conferences/Standardization Meetings Attended
- Status of publications
- Status of talks given by the partner
- Any other important achievements related to the project.

5.2 Cost Claim Reports

The Cost Claim reports should be sent to the coordinator and the work package leaders five (5) working days after the end of the reporting period for the technical issues, and 2 weeks for the financial part. The coordinator will provide appropriate template. The Cost Claim Reports will include at least the following issues:

- Planned Resources per activity per work package
- Actual Resources per activity per work package
- Cumulative Resources per activity per work package
- Consumables
- Travel Expenses
- Hardware/Software expenses
- Audit Reports

5.3 Responsibility Assignment

Based on the SENTINEL Description of Action (DoA), the PC assigns and manages the WPLs to achieve the objective of each work package. The PC keeps an action items list, detailing the open issues of the work packages, task, the deadline, the partner that has been assigned the task, a small description, and the issue status (open, assigned, closed, postponed, delayed). The tasks are assigned to the partners based on their contributions to the DoA, their area of expertise and their resources in the project as reflected by the relevant Person Months (PM).

5.4 Deliverables

Project deliverables to the European Commission (with the exception of the Periodic or Final Reports) serve as the outcome of Work Package technical progress. They consist of a combination of documents such as written reports as well as potential non-document prototype releases. The European Commission requires that all non-document deliverables be documented appropriately as a written report. The intention of the deliverable review process is to ensure that the document has been reviewed by a broad spectrum of individuals.

5.5 Quality Assurance Process

The Quality Assurance Process aims to assure the quality of the project deliverables and the quality of the deliverables' review process. To this end, it aims to establish an effective baseline for the project's quality controls and a secure means of achieving deliverables that are fit for purpose. The Quality Assurance Plan has been presented in detail in Deliverable D8.5. Here, we provide a summary of the main principles that must be followed to ensure that quality is ensured at all stages of the project.

5.5.1 Roles and Responsibilities

The following roles are involved in the quality assurance process.

- The PC is accountable for formally approving the version to be sent to the EC.
- The QAM is responsible for setting the mechanism for reviewing progress against the quality assurance criteria, for setting the quality assurance criteria for the deliverables (see Section 5.5.2), and for coordinating and providing guidance for the evaluation activities of the deliverables.
- The STIM is responsible for the scientific and technical cohesion and excellence of the project.
- For each deliverable, the deliverable leader is responsible for the overall quality of the deliverable and for ensuring that all comments of the internal reviewers (see Section 5.5.2) are properly addressed. Each partner is responsible for the quality of their contribution in the deliverable.
- The deliverable team is responsible for supporting the deliverable leader in addressing the comments made by the peer reviewers.
- Internal peer reviewers are the SENTINEL partners responsible for the completion of the internal review of the deliverable (prior to sending it to the EC).

5.5.2 Deliverable Preparation, Internal Review and Approval Process

The main editor of each deliverable is the corresponding deliverable leader (see Table 7). For each deliverable, two reviewers (ideally with no involvement in the specific deliverable) are appointed by the QAM. The internal reviewers should inspect the deliverable and provide comments to the deliverable leader. These comments are sent to the author inline as part of the working document with revisions marked-up, using the “track changes” feature, whenever possible. A review summary should also be submitted through the dedicated Peer Review Document, which is located in the same folder as the deliverable in the project’s file repository (NextCloud) for quality assurance purposes.

The SENTINEL deliverables list and the corresponding internal reviewers appointed by the QAM has been updated after The Shell termination and are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. List of deliverables and internal reviewers

No.	Del. Title	Leader	Type	Delivery Date	Reviewer #1	Reviewer #2
D1.1	The SENTINEL baseline	IDIR	R	09/2021	UNINOVA	ITML
D1.2	The SENTINEL technical architecture	INTRA	R	11/2021	ITML	TIG
D1.3	The SENTINEL experimentation protocol	IDIR	R	11/2021	ITML	LIST
D2.1	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: MVP	ITML	DEM	05/2022	INTRA	ACS
D2.2	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: 1 st complete version	FP	DEM	11/2022	UNINOVA	FP
D2.3	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: Final version	LIST	DEM	11/2023	ITML	UNINOVA
D2.4	Continuous data privacy legislation compliance monitoring and guidelines – interim version	CECL	R	11/2022	INTRA	IDIR
D2.5	Continuous data privacy legislation compliance monitoring and guidelines – final version	CECL	R	11/2023	AEGIS	FP
D3.1	The SENTINEL digital core: MVP	ITML	DEM	05/2022	ACS	TSI
D3.2	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: 1 st complete version	FP	DEM	11/2022	CG	ACS
D3.3	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: Final version	LIST	DEM	11/2023	TIG	UNINOVA
D4.1	The SENTINEL services: MVP	IDIR	DEM	05/2022	LIST	ITML
D4.2	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: 1 st complete version	STS	DEM	11/2022	TSI	ITML
D4.3	The SENTINEL data protection and cybersecurity offerings: Final version	ACS	DEM	11/2023	CG	ACS

D5.1	The SENTINEL visualisation and UI component – first version	AEGIS	DEM	05/2022	ITML	STS
D5.2	The SENTINEL visualisation and UI component – second version	AEGIS	DEM	11/2022	ITML	INTRA
D5.3	The SENTINEL visualisation and UI component – final version	AEGIS	DEM	11/2023	ACS	ITML
D5.4	The SENTINEL Minimum Viable Product	INTRA	R+DEM	05/2022	ITML	AEGIS
D5.5	The SENTINEL integrated solution – interim version	INTRA	R+DEM	11/2022	FP	IDIR
D5.6	The SENTINEL integrated solution – final version	INTRA	R+DEM	11/2023	LIST	TIG
D5.7	Best practices for maintaining and operating the system in the long-term – TRL 7	UNINOVA	R	05/2024	CG	ITML
D6.1	SENTINEL Demonstration - initial execution and evaluation	TIG	R	11/2022	ITML	IDIR
D6.2	SENTINEL Demonstration - final execution	CG	R	11/2023	FP	AEGIS
D6.3	Assessment report and impact analysis	STS	R	05/2024	TSI	LIST
D7.1	The SENTINEL website and visual identity	ITML	R+DEM	07/2021	UNINOVA	CECL
D7.2	Market analysis and preliminary business modelling	AEGIS	R	11/2021	INTRA	ACS
D7.3	Dissemination strategy and activities – interim version	UNINOVA	R	11/2022	ITML	AEGIS
D7.4	Dissemination strategy and activities – final version	UNINOVA	R	05/2024	STS	ITML
D7.5	Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – interim version	UNINOVA	R	11/2022	CECL	FP
D7.6	Ecosystem building and SMEs engagement report – final version	UNINOVA	R	05/2024	AEGIS	FP
D7.7	Exploitation strategy, standardisation activities and best practices – interim version	STS	R	11/2022	INTRA	AEGIS
D7.8	Exploitation strategy, standardisation activities and best practices – final version	STS	R	05/2024	ITML	ACS
D7.9	Final business model, market analysis and long-term sustainability report	AEGIS	R	05/2024	IDIR	INTRA
D8.1	Yearly project management report – first version	ITML	R	05/2022	AEGIS	IDIR
D8.2	Yearly project management report – second version	ITML	R	05/2023	INTRA	IDIR
D8.3	Yearly project management report – third version	ITML	R	05/2024	IDIR	STS
D8.4	Risk identification and management & quality plan	ITML	R	11/2021	TSI	IDIR
D8.5	The SENTINEL QA plan and periodic monitoring report – first version	ITML	R	08/2021	IDIR	AEGIS
D8.6	The SENTINEL QA plan and periodic monitoring report – second version	ITML	R	11/2022	FP	INTRA

D8.7	The SENTINEL QA plan and periodic monitoring report – final version	ITML	R	05/2024	INTRA	CECL
D8.8	The SENTINEL project handbook – first version	ITML	R	09/2021	CECL	INTRA
D8.9	The SENTINEL data management plan	ITML	ORDP	11/2021	TSI	STS
D8.10	The SENTINEL project handbook – first version	ITML	R	05/2022	ACS	IDIR
D8.11	The SENTINEL project handbook – first version	ITML	R	05/2023	STS	IDIR
D8.12	The SENTINEL technical and innovation management report – interim version	INTRA	R	11/2022	AEGIS	ACS
D8.13	The SENTINEL technical and innovation management report – final version	INTRA	R	05/2024	ITML	STS
D8.14	Ethics manual and ethical controlling report – interim version	CECL	R	11/2022	ITML	FP
D8.15	Ethics manual and ethical controlling report – final version	CECL	R	05/2024	CG	LIST
D9.1	POPD – Requirement No. 1	ITML	Ethics	09/2021	CECL	FP

As indicated in Table 8, each deliverable is first examined by the QAM, followed by the internal reviewers when it is complete. Peer reviewers need to review the deliverable and inform the WPL, and QAM when the review is finished. Subsequently, it is re-examined by the deliverable leader to confirm that reviewers’ comments have been successfully addressed and by the QAM in order to confirm that the review process has been followed. Finally, it is approved by the PC who submits the deliverable to the EC website.

5.5.3 Procedure and Timing

As indicated in Table 9, the deadlines (see column **when**) are indicative but strongly recommended and correspond to a minimum number of weeks in advance of formal submission deadlines. They may be customised, in agreement between the role bearing responsibility (**who**) and the roles monitoring adherence to each step (what), for documented reasons, such as the size of the deliverable, actual work progress or other unforeseen circumstances. In all cases, however, deliverables should be ready at least one week in advance of their formal deadlines.

It is expected that each deliverable will use its own dedicated space on the shared NextCloud repository, where draft versions, final versions before review, reviews, and final version to be submitted will be uploaded and stored. It is particularly important that all partners make active use of NextCloud. It is expected that deliverable leaders will keep uploading draft versions of their deliverables on a regular basis to help other partners stay in touch with ongoing work and how it develops, identify any possible issues early, and so on.

Table 9. Overview of deliverable preparation, review, and submission process

Step	When	Who	What
1	8 weeks	Deliverable Leader	Sets up the deliverable structure – Table of Contents (ToC) and coordinates the creation of the deliverable.
	4 weeks		Sends the draft to the work package leader for a 1 st review.

2	2-4 weeks	WPL	Evaluates the deliverable and either accepts it and forwards it to the QAM for peer review or returns it back to the Deliverable Leader with recommendations
3	2-4 weeks	Deliverable Leader	Addresses any feedback from the WPL and sends the latest version to the QAM
4	2-3 weeks	Quality Manager	Evaluates the deliverable and either forwards it to the pre-assigned peer reviewers or returns it to the Deliverable Leader with recommendations
5	2 weeks	Internal Reviewers	Provide comments / feedback to Deliverable Leader, copying QAM.
6	1-2 weeks	Deliverable Leader	Submits final version of the deliverable for submission to PC, copying WPL and QAM. WPL and/or reviewers need to confirm that the review comments have been addressed before the Deliverable Leader submits the deliverable to the PC.
7	1-2 weeks	PC	Approves and uploads the deliverable to the EC services.

5.5.4 Document Deliverable Template

To assure consistency and uniform appearance a universal MS Word template will be used for all deliverables (see Section 3.3). The template defines a series of quality controls for project deliverables and provides a series of features that enhance quality of the documents, such as:

- a proper front page with all the necessary logos and project/document information,
- appropriate headers and footers providing useful document and document navigation information,
- all necessary disclaimers and copyright information,
- a concise overview of all document information,
- a table presenting all document history (changes) from initial draft to final document,
- a table of contents and lists of figures and tables,
- an executive summary of the document,
- acronyms and abbreviations table, and
- a uniform formatting templates.

5.5.5 Deliverable Quality Assurance Criteria

Table 10 provides a list of quality indicators, approved by the QAM, in the form of a checklist to be completed by the internal reviewers. This checklist forms the basis of the Deliverable Review Sheet that will accompany each deliverable.

Table 10. Reviewer checklist

Aspect	Indicators
Relevance	The deliverable is relevant to SENTINEL and to the particular WP activities.
Methodological framework soundness	Results are based upon a clear methodology, involving users' test, expert opinions, etc.
Quality of achievements	Results are of high value and as expected.
Quality of presentation of achievements	Results are adequately explained and commented. The deliverable's contributions to the project's scientific/business objectives and the introduced

	novelties are concisely described, in terms of added value from the scientific/business/technical perspectives.
Deliverable layout / spelling / format	<p>FORMAT: The deliverable complies with the project’s deliverables template formatting; (i) the table of contents, lists of abbreviations, tables, and figures have been inspected for errors/omissions; (ii) the correct spacing, numbering, and page breaks have been checked for all pages; (iii) the references comply with the Harvard Citation Style. The bibliography is formatted correctly, and all references are cited in the text; (iv) appendices are identified in sequence by number or letter.</p> <p>LAYOUT: The deliverable includes all necessary chapters; (i) it has a 1-page Executive Summary which clearly summarizes the deliverable’s findings along with the potential scientific, technical, or business value; (ii) the deliverable’s objectives are clearly stated in the introductory section. More specifically, the document should contain a brief and concise introduction (1-2 pages long) where the purpose and scope, the relation to other Work Packages/Deliverables, the contribution to WP and project objectives, and the document’s outline are clearly stated; SPELLING: (i) language usage is appropriate for the audience, the text is clear and concise, the grammar and overall writing style are of high quality, and the grammar/spelling checks are complete;</p>
General comments	These refer to any issue not covered by the particular topics below. They may refer to thoroughness of general contents, correspondence of the reported work to the project’s objectives as in the Description of Action and correspondence to the general programme objectives.

6. Meetings

6.1 Plenary Project Meetings

The plenary project meetings will take place periodically every four (4) months, or ad hoc in case an outstanding technical issue calls for an additional meeting. The meetings will be initiated by the PC. In some cases, it may be initiated by a WPL, but approved a-priori by the PC. Scheduled meetings will be announced at least 4 weeks in advance and an effort will be made to be scheduled at the end of the current plenary meeting. In outstanding circumstances, attendees will be notified 1 week in advance, given that at least 75% of the participating partners are available. Other important items about the plenary meeting include:

- Agenda and supporting documentation will be available to all attendees at least 4 weeks (for physical attendance) or 1 week (for remote attendance) before the meeting. Issuing of all documents will be via the PC.
- All meetings will have minutes written by the PC (or a substitute if necessary) or the respective WPL if the meeting concerns a specific work package. Unless otherwise agreed in the meeting, minutes will be issued within 14 calendar days of the completion of the meeting. Minutes will take the form of action items to keep things short and to the point.
- The action items list will be maintained in a file in the NextCloud, available for all project partners.
- The first task in each meeting will be the agreement on the agenda and the last one agreement on the date and place of the next meeting.

6.2 General Assembly Meetings

GA meetings are initiated by the PC and occur at least four times a year (physically or virtually). GA meetings will also take place in case very important technical, or non-technical (administrative) issues have to be faced. For example, a General Assembly meeting may result in modifying the project consortium, change the project objectives or even terminate the project.

- All partners will be notified at least 4 weeks (for physical attendance) or 1 week (for remote attendance) in advance.
- Agenda and supporting documentation will be available to all attendees at least 4 weeks (for physical attendance) or 1 week (for remote attendance) before the meeting. Issuing of all documents will be via the PC, who is responsible for compiling all submissions from partners.
- All meetings will have minutes written by the PC or his representative. Unless otherwise agreed in the meeting, minutes will be issued within 1 week of the completion of the meeting.

To minimize expenses and save time, General Assembly meetings will take place in parallel to plenary meetings, if feasible. The first task in each meeting will be the agreement on the agenda and the last one agreement on the date and place of the next meeting.

6.3 Review Preparation Meetings

Review preparation meetings are expected to take place the day(s) before the project reviews. The PC and all WPLs are expected to attend the review preparation meetings. Other members of the project will be expected to attend when required. As the review preparation meetings will form a major forum for the exchange of information in addition to the management of the project, all consortium members will be encouraged to attend. The review preparation meetings will also review progress against the project success criteria and will report to the GA all deviations from planned progress, together with an action plan to recover any shortfalls or exploit any gains in the programme. All meetings will have minutes written by the PC.

6.4 Conferences/Presentations/Exhibitions

SENTINEL will try to promote the visibility of the project. Thus, participation in conferences, dissemination activities and standardization bodies will be actively pursued. The following rules should be applied:

- When the expenses are claimed during cost claims, the project has to be officially mentioned and this has to be proven by official documentation/contribution, e.g., an acknowledgement in a paper, use the proper logos in posters, etc. The typical text for the acknowledgement to the EC for its funding is as follows:

“This [paper/presentation/work/research/...] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101021659”.

- The conference/presentation/contribution documentation has to be uploaded on the web server.
- When the project is official mentioned or presented, the PC should be notified two (2) weeks before the event. The reason for this is to homogenize potential duplication or conflicting contributions/presentations.
- It is recommended to include a disclaimer on every publication/presentation. Typical text is as follows:

This [paper/presentation/...] reflects only the authors’ views and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

7 Risk Management

Risks for the implementation of the project as well as the procedures that will be followed to mitigate them in case they materialize, as identified in the beginning of the project, and listed in the Grant Agreement, are described in Table 11.

Table 11. Identification of risks and mitigation measures

Risk No.	Description of risk	WP No.	Risk mitigation measures
1	Underperforming partner Probability: low Impact: medium	All	All consortium partners are highly committed to the project and it is hardly to expect this situation. If it occurs, the flexible project management structure and Consortium Agreement allow a quick shift of resources to alternative project partners.
2	Partner leaving the project Probability: low Impact: high	All	This unlikely event would only have a temporarily disruptive effect, since the consortium is well balanced with a balanced complementarity and overlap of competences, simplifying allocating any affected tasks to another partner. Otherwise, the flexible management structure allows the quick inclusion of new partners in the consortium if necessary.
3	Key person left or is temporarily not available Probability: medium Impact: medium	All	Consortium partners are involved in the related areas with more than one staff member, ensuring an immediate substitution. Furthermore, the project as whole has technical excellence in related disciplines spread across the partners, providing additional substitution possibilities.
4	Needed partners' resources are underestimated Probability: low Impact: medium	All	In this case, the project management bodies will analyse the following possibilities to ensure that planned work can be completed: (i) rearranging resources among the partners as needed; (ii) committing further internal resources of organisations in project activities (if possible); and (iii) re-planning work on the activities in accordance with previous measures.
5	Project schedule is partly not appropriate Probability: low Impact: medium	All	The project management structure and measures continuously monitor performed work vs. project plan and are entitled to perform corrective actions – change of the project plan – if necessary, which also apply for this case (see also below). In crucial cases, the STIM will work on the plan adaptation in close cooperation with the EC.
6	Project milestones or deliverables are delayed Probability: medium Impact: low	All	In the scope of project management monitoring activities, detailed analysis will be done on both global project and lower (WP/Task) project implementation levels. Thus, it will be ensured that such cases are recognised in early stages, ensuring timely and effective implementation of necessary corrections in the work plan.
7	Agreement among partners is difficult to achieve Probability: low Impact: medium	All	The collaboration spirit in the consortium targets to achieve consensus among all partners on the open issues and the project management bodies will work in this direction. However, to avoid too long consensus making processes, which might affect the project plan, the related management procedures for decision making and conflict resolution will be timely applied.

8	Not satisfactory interaction among WP's and tasks Probability: low Impact: medium	All	The regular synchronisation of work among WPs (as well as among tasks within WPs) will be performed in the scope of project management activities, so that these cases should not occur or should be timely recognised allowing implementation of corrective actions without significant impact on the project plan. If the problems continue, the PC together with the STIM and WPLs will analyse problems in interactions and propose additional procedures for improvement of the interactions.
9	Necessary coordination level is not achieved Probability: low Impact: impact	All	Similar as it will be done for monitoring of the technical project activities, including analysis of work done and implementation of the corrective actions, the project coordination and management will be observed as well. Thus, if necessary, the responsible management bodies will propose the corrective actions improving overall project coordination. If needed, management of the Coordinator organisation will be involved to solve the problems.
10	Problems in integrating the different components in a common platform Probability: medium Impact: medium	5	An agile approach has been proposed for the SENTINEL implementation lifecycle to ensure efficient integration; SENTINEL technical partners have significant expertise in platforms/systems' integration.
11	Low technical quality of deliverables Probability: low Impact: high	All	This risk is mitigated through regular and thorough quality reviews and the internal peer reviewing of each deliverable.
12	SENTINEL modules do not perform as expected in terms of accuracy and efficiency with respect to compliance levels, recommendation accuracy and data protection Probability: low Impact: high	2-6	SENTINEL modules rely on a number of existing technologies and tools that have been validated and are brought in by the consortium partners. On top of that, the SENTINEL agile development schedule has foreseen the deployment of two versions of the components, facilitating thus their continuous improvement and validation by the SENTINEL end users throughout the project's duration.
13	The final platform is not user-friendly Probability: low Impact: medium	4,5	Advanced visualisation techniques will be utilised by highly experienced partners to ensure the implementation of a user-friendly platform.
14	Not enough stakeholders are reached to exploit SENTINEL & ensure sustainability Probability: medium Impact: medium	7	SENTINEL consortium already comprises critical stakeholders with respect to ecosystem building, led by UNINOVA and the links with digital innovation hubs and incubators. On top of that, a specific task (T7.4) has been allocated to ensure stakeholders' engagement; all SENTINEL partners have existing communication channels to ensure the project's sustainability.
15	Market's rapid changes jeopardise SENTINEL sustainability and expected impact Probability: low Impact: medium	7	Market will be continuously analysed throughout the project and the necessary adaptation will be made to the SENTINEL business plan in order to ensure that the platform's impact in the market is maximised. To ensure the viability of the task, a combination of an academic partner with a partner closer to the market are leading these activities.

A more detailed and updated risk identification and management plan is presented as part of Deliverable D8.4 Risk identification and management & quality plan (due in M6 – November 2021).

The presented “Identification of risks and mitigation measures” table, should be updated in the final version of this deliverable, to state any new risks which have been raised within the project life.

8 Conclusion

The SENTINEL's project handbook aims to specify all procedures within the project's lifecycle, including a) general internal management procedures and roles, b) decision mechanisms, c) communication between partners, d) partner's contact information, e) document management, including deliverable review and submission procedures (as part of the project's quality assurance process), f) procedures for dispute resolution, g) reporting procedures and template.

This deliverable is the second version of "The SENTINEL project handbook" which submitted on M12 and will be accomplished in the 3rd and final version in M24.

The project handbook should be used by all SENTINEL partners as a reference manual during the implementation of the action.

Appendix A – Technical reporting template

Quarterly Reporting Form

Partner Short Name

Month Year

Please fill in below the details regarding your contribution to SENTINEL during the reporting period. At the end of the document, there are instructions (in italic print) on how to fill in each section. You should delete any parts of this document that are not applicable to your organization in this reporting period. When submitting this report, please feel free to attach any supplemental material you find appropriate.

1. Progress per Work Package

1.1 WP1 – SENTINEL baseline: Setting the methodological scene

1.1.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- technical changes (if applicable)*
- major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 1

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.1.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ -1 page per task to be written by task leader

T1.1 The SENTINEL requirements engineering methodology

T1.2 Technology convergence: the SENTINEL offerings and updated architecture

T1.3 The SENTINEL demonstration execution protocol

1.1.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

ITML	TX.X: TX.Y:
LIST	TX.X:
IDIR	...
INTRA	...
STS	...
AEGIS	...
TSI	...
ACS	...
UNINOVA	...
CG	...
TIG	...
CECL	...
FP	...

1.1.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g., technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.2 WP2 – The SENTINEL privacy and personal data protection technologies

1.2.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 2

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.2.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ -1 page per task to be written by task leader

T2.1 The privacy and data protection compliance framework

T2.2 The integrated Identity Management System: enabling a unified European Personal Data space

T2.3 Contributed cybersecurity components

T2.4 Continuous management and integration of opensource technology offerings and solutions

T2.5 GDPR and data protection regulations continuous monitoring and guidelines

1.2.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

<i>ITML</i>	<i>TX.X:</i> <i>TX.Y:</i>
<i>LIST</i>	<i>TX.X:</i>
<i>IDIR</i>	...
<i>INTRA</i>	...
<i>STS</i>	...
<i>AEGIS</i>	...
<i>TSI</i>	...
<i>ACS</i>	...
<i>UNINOVA</i>	...
<i>CG</i>	...
<i>TIG</i>	...
<i>CECL</i>	...
<i>FP</i>	...

1.2.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.3 WP3 – The SENTINEL digital core

1.3.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- technical changes (if applicable)*
- major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 3

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.3.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ -1 page per task to be written by task leader

T3.1 Access and monitoring of open security data sharing platforms

T3.2 The incident handling and sharing module

T3.3 The intelligent recommendation engine

T3.4 Policy drafting, enforcement and orchestration module

1.3.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

<i>ITML</i>	<i>TX.X:</i> <i>TX.Y:</i>
<i>LIST</i>	<i>TX.X:</i>
<i>IDIR</i>	...
<i>INTRA</i>	...
<i>STS</i>	...
<i>AEGIS</i>	...
<i>TSI</i>	...
<i>ACS</i>	...
<i>UNINOVA</i>	...
<i>CG</i>	...
<i>TIG</i>	...
<i>CECL</i>	...
<i>FP</i>	...

1.3.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.4 WP4 – The SENTINEL services

1.4.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 4

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.4.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ - 1 page per task to be written by task leader

T4.1 Advanced CyberRange simulations and training for SMEs/MEs

T4.2 Data protection impact assessment and assurance

T4.3 Tailor-made requirement analyses via self-assessment, training and RASE scoring

T4.4 The SENTINEL Observatory

1.4.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

ITML	TX.X: TX.Y:
LIST	TX.X:
IDIR	...
INTRA	...
STS	...
AEGIS	...
TSI	...

ACS	...
UNINOVA	...
CG	...
TIG	...
CECL	...
FP	...

1.4.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.5 WP5 – SENTINEL continuous integration and system validation

1.5.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 5

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.5.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ -1 page per task to be written by task leader

T5.1 Interactive visualisations and front-end components

T5.2 Continuous integration towards the realization of a complete system

T5.3 From the prototype to the final solution

1.5.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

ITML	TX.X: TX.Y:
LIST	TX.X:
IDIR	...
INTRA	...
STS	...
AEGIS	...
TSI	...
ACS	...
UNINOVA	...
CG	...
TIG	...
CECL	...
FP	...

1.5.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.6 WP6 – Real-life experimental evaluations: SENTINEL pilots

1.6.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 6

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.6.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ - 1 page per task to be written by task leader

T6.1 SENTINEL experimentation protocol alignment and pilots' setup

T6.2 Validating SENTINEL offerings to SMEs and MMs: Test cases in the fields of genomics and social care

T6.3 Open access to the SENTINEL platform for validation and evaluation through Digital Innovation Hubs

T6.4 Evaluation and impact analysis

1.6.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

ITML	TX.X: TX.Y:
LIST	TX.X:
IDIR	...
INTRA	...
STS	...
AEGIS	...
TSI	...
ACS	...
UNINOVA	...
CG	...
TIG	...
CECL	...
FP	...

1.6.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.7 WP7 – Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management

1.7.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 7

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.7.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ -1 page per task to be written by task leader

T7.1 Market continuous analysis and business planning for SENTINEL exploitation

T7.2 Dissemination and communication strategy to trigger awareness and new business opportunities

T7.3 Exploitation and standardization activities and best practices

T7.4 SENTINEL ecosystem building: Continuous engagement of technology providers, SMEs/MEs

1.7.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

ITML	TX.X: TX.Y:
LIST	TX.X:
IDIR	...
INTRA	...
STS	...
AEGIS	...
TSI	...
ACS	...
UNINOVA	...
CG	...
TIG	...
CECL	...
FP	...

1.7.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.8 WP8 – Project Management, coordination and quality assurance

1.8.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 8

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.8.2 Key achievements during reporting period at task level

Recommendation: ½ - 1 page per task to be written by task leader

T8.1 Project Quality Planning and Monitoring

T8.2 Day-to-day management, project & financial control and resource monitoring

T8.3 Technical and innovation management

T8.4 Ethics and Data Protection

1.8.3 Work carried out in this work package per partner

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

ITML	TX.X: TX.Y:
LIST	TX.X:
IDIR	...
INTRA	...
STS	...
AEGIS	...
TSI	...
ACS	...
UNINOVA	...
CG	...
TIG	...
CECL	...
FP	...

1.8.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

1.9 WP9 – Ethics requirements

1.9.1 Summary of results achieved during reporting period

Recommendation: ½ -1 page to be written by WP leader (WP leader view)

Please, comment also on:

- *the current status with respect to planning (any deviations from plan or delays, see table below)*
- *deliverables submitted (if applicable)*
- *technical changes (if applicable)*
- *major risks and (if applicable) fallback solutions etc.*

Table x. Table Deviations for Work Package 9

Deviations from work plan			
Task #	Start / End date Planned	Start / end date Actual	Reason for deviation

1.9.3 Work carried out in this work package

Recommendation: ¼ - ½ page (excluding diagrams) to be written by each partner.

<i>ITML</i>	
-------------	--

1.9.4 Deviations from Work Plan

If applicable, each partner, please comment on any deviations from work plan occurred during this reporting period, e.g. technical changes, resources, delays, etc.

2. Status of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable DX.X was completed....

3. Attendance to Conferences and Meetings

Please, fill the table with the conferences and/or meetings that were attended by members of your organization and relate with the work on SENTINEL. Use the “Type” column to indicate how each meeting relates with the project. Use one of the following types: SENTINEL meeting, SENTINEL funded, SENTINEL related.

Meeting	Location	Date	Attendee(s)	Type
“xxx”	...	XX/XX/2021	...	

4. Status of papers and articles

In this section, you should report any SENTINEL-related papers and articles authored by your organization. Make sure that the reported papers and articles give proper credit to the SENTINEL project. If your paper/article undergoes a review, use the “Update” column to outline its progress. Use one of the following indications: Submitted, Accepted, Presented.

Title	Author(s)	Conference	Update	Date
“xxx”		XX/XX/2021

5. SENTINEL publicity

Report here any SENTINEL publicity events that you became aware of. Try to include screenshots or URLs when possible. The events could (but don’t have to) relate with your organizations.

-

6. Talks hosted by SENTINEL partners

In this section, you should report any talks on subjects related to SENTINEL that you hosted during this reporting period.

Title	Speaker	Event	Date

7. Issues

Report here things that will affect the work on the project, while not directly related to some work package (e.g., financial issues).

8. Other

Report here everything regarding SENTINEL that you feel that should be reported to the EC and does not match one of the sections above.

Appendix B – Peer review document template

Peer review document

Overall Peer Review Result

Deliverable is:

<input type="checkbox"/> Fully accepted	<input type="checkbox"/> Accepted with minor comments	<input type="checkbox"/> Rejected unless modified as suggested	<input type="checkbox"/> Rejected
---	---	--	-----------------------------------

Specific peer review criteria:

- 1. Relevance** - “Is this deliverable relevant to SENTINEL and to the particular WP activities it covers?”
- 2. Methodological framework soundness** - “Are the results arbitrary or based upon a clear methodology, involving users’ test, expert opinions, etc.?”
- 3. Quality of achievements** – “Are the results of high value and as expected”?
- 4. Quality of presentation of achievements** – “Are the results adequately explained and commented?”
- 5. Deliverable layout / spelling / format** – “Does the deliverable include all necessary chapters; is it readable in comprehensive language, etc.?”

COMMENTS OF PEER REVIEWER

General comments

These refer to any issue not covered by the particular topics below. They may refer to thoroughness of general contents, correspondence of the reported work to the project's objectives as in the Description of Action and correspondence to the general programme objectives.

Appendix D – Deliverables template

Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe

Dx.1- Title of deliverable

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101021659
Project Acronym	SENTINEL
Project Full Title	Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe
Starting Date	1 st June 2021
Duration	36 months
Call Identifier	H2020-SU-DS-2020
Topic	H2020-SU-DS-2018-2019-2020 Digital Security and privacy for citizens and Small and Medium Enterprises and Micro Enterprises
Project Website	https://www.sentinel-project.eu/
Project Coordinator	Dr. George Bravos
Organisation	Information Technology for Market Leadership (ITML)
Email	gebravos@itml.gr

Document Information

Work Package	Work package x
Deliverable Title	
Version	x.x (starting from 1.0)
Date of Submission	DD/MM/YYYY
Main Editor(s)	Name Surname (Organisation)
Contributor(s)	Name Surname (Organisation), Name Surname (Organisation),

Reviewer(s)	Name Surname (Organisation), (Organisation),	Name Surname (Organisation),
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Document Classification							
Draft	X	Final		Confidential	X	Public	

History			
Version	Issue Date	Status	Distribution
1.0	DD/MM/YYYY	Draft or Final	Public or Confidential
1.1		

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation

Executive Summary

Text here

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Document

Text here

1.2. Structure of the Document

Text here

1.3. Intended readership

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2. Section

2.2. Subsection

Figure 1. Figure legend here

2.3. Subsection

Table x. Table legend here

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4

3. Section

Conclusion

Text here

References

- [1] Use Harvard style for reference list and bibliography